

"FORTE OF ZOROASTRIANISM"
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Abstract :

Parsi, one of the most successful migrant minority group in world. They are well known for their famous funeral tradition of building tower to be eaten by vultures and scientists, artists which become world famous. They played an important role in country's freedom struggle. Later it become one of the shrinking community, as they would marry within the community. Late marriage, health complications all contributed to falling birth rate. Late marriages leads to infertility problem to women. A fertility program was launched by the Indian Ministry of Minority Affairs and the Parzor Foundation, an Non Governmental Organization (NGO). Conversion of people from other religion into Zoroastrianism is also not allowed, as they believed that pure parsi bloodlines will be eliminated in a few generations. Even though they are tiny community, today Parsis such as Tata, Godrej and Wadia families are among top corporate companies.

Key words: *C*

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Introduction :

Zoroastrianism is one of the oldest Iranian religion, based on the teaching of prophet of Iran who follows organized faith. It believes in that there is judgement after the death. The Parsi community's work is deeply incorporated with the rise of modern India. They adopted quickly to the British colonial rule. After independence they filled key roles in trade, science and industry.

Parsi Community :

Parsi numbers have declined by 12% every census decade. An infusion of fresh blood is desperately needed. Admitting children of all mixed marriages would substantially improve the statistics, but will dilute even destroy, a very distinctive ethnic identity. Mumbai's extreme wealth disparity has earned it the moniker of the world's most expensive slum.

Apartments like the ones in the Parsi colonies-spacious, well maintained and low in cost are hard to come by in Mumbai. Their interiors are blend of British and Chinese influences, from Victorian motifs carved into oak bed frames to porcelain vases obtained through trade with mainland China.

Conclusion :

The Parsis now ran community medical centres, ambulance corps, scouting troops, clubs. They had their own charitable foundations, housing, estates, legal institutions, courts, and governance. Even while maintaining their own cultural identity they did not fail to recognize themselves as nationally Indian.

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